

NON-MONOTONIC TENSILE TESTS ON POLYMERIC COMPOSITES :
MODELING THE NONLINEARITY.

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ABSTRACT

The topic of this work is to present a modeling of the nonlinearity of the lamina suitable for tensile tests including loadings and unloadings. Only the in-plane behaviour is concerned.

The mechanical properties of the lamina are supposed to depend on the actual shear strain and on the extremum shear strains attained during the loading history.

It must be emphasized that this model is quite simple as it depends only on 7 parameters (4 initial elastic moduli, 1 parameter to describe the first loading and 2 parameters to describe the unloading/reloading loops) and one variable (maximum shear strain) through analytic functions, making it easy to include in FEM codes if necessary.

KEYWORDS: loading, uniaxial; modeling; nonlinear; plasticity; shear.

1. INTRODUCTION

The behavior of fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composites depends on the mechanical properties of the fibers, which can be considered as elastic, and on those of the polymeric matrix. It must be recognized that solid polymers have both viscoelastic and plastic properties, which may not be apparent under the same circumstances. Viscoelastic effects are apparent in vibration or ultrasonic measurements, when very small amounts of strains are

concerned, and will also govern long term responses such as creep or strain recovery. Plasticity appears when large strains are involved, particularly shear strains. This is very clear in the classical off-axis tensile test, where partial unloadings will show important amounts of irrecoverable strain. However, it has been shown that bulk polymer could undergo huge plastic shear strains (up to 0.6) in the so-called shear bands (1). We think that the particular geometry of in-situ matrix in long fibers composites may enhance its ability to deform plastically in shear between the fibers. Such a phenomenon has been suggested in metal matrix composites (2).

Many authors have proposed models to describe the nonlinearity of the shear response of the unidirectional ply (3-6). Here, we will extend a work (7) concerning monotonic tensile tests, where we discuss in more details the relevancy of choosing the "plastic" point of view.

The model we propose lies within the framework of plasticity, as the mechanical properties (the shear and transverse moduli) of the lamina are supposed to depend on some kinematic variables. We present a comparison between the experimental responses to non-monotonic tensile tests and theoretical ones computed with an incremental procedure.

2. MATERIAL AND TEST

Two samples of unidirectional glass/epoxy have been tested in an off-axis configuration. The material is a general purpose composite manufactured by the French company STRUCTIL and referenced VEE-2 20/R368. The fiber volume fraction has been found equal to $V_f = 54.9 \pm 0.8 \%$. The overall dimensions of the samples are $200 \times 12 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^2$, and they are provided with 35 mm aluminium end tabs bonded with Loctite® Blackmax 180, this yielding an active length of 130 mm corresponding to an aspect ratio greater than 10. The samples are equipped with one $0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ$ rosette in the middle of one side, and the error of alignment of the 0° gauge along the specimen axis has been found less than 1° . The experimental data are logged on a AT-type computer, and strains are corrected of the systematic error induced by the quarter bridge setup. The shear strain is extracted from the rosette

measurements and the shear stress from the load, and the tangent shear modulus of the unidirectional is obtained by derivative of the shear stress/shear strain curve.

The test consists of loadings at a controlled axial strain rate of $0.1 \text{ \%} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ up to an intermediate level of strain, followed by unloadings at the same speed until a prescribed load level is reached. After those unloadings, some time is allowed for strain recovery, in order to obtain a well defined state to begin a new cycle. A typical cycle is sketched in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Typical loading/unloading cycle

Two such tests were performed:

- $[15]_{4S}$ with unloadings when $\epsilon_x = 0.8 \text{ \%}$, 1.6 \% and 2.4 \% ; load during recovery about 2 \% of ultimate load;
- $[45]_{4S}$ with unloadings when $\epsilon_x = 0.4 \text{ \%}$, 0.8 \% , 1.2 \% , 1.6 \% ; load during recovery about 1 \% of ultimate load.

The experimental responses are represented with solid lines in Figures 4-5.

3. MODEL

In Figures 4-5, it is apparent that after an unloading/loading loop, the experimental curve keeps close to a "master curve" which is simply the response to a monotonic loading, as we have checked. So, the *monotonic first loading curve* can be seen as the hardening curve of the material.

The model we propose for that hardening curve is derived from

the one presented in ref. (7) which has been applied to various materials. The basic idea is that the tangent shear modulus of an unidirectional ply undergoes a dramatic decrease during off-axis or $[\pm 45]_S$ tests, which may be accurately represented by an exponential function with respect to the shear strain. Rather than the shear strain ϵ_6 in the material axes (subscripts 1,2,6), we prefer to represent the actual kinematic state by the second invariant, or maximum engineering shear strain R :

$$R = \sqrt{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)^2 + \epsilon_6^2} \quad (1)$$

So, our model writes:

$$G = (G_0 - G_1) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-R}{R_6}\right) + G_1 \quad (2)$$

The longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli and the Poisson's ratio are assumed constants. Apart from the initial moduli E_1 , ν_{12} , E_2 and G_0 , the model depends on the logarithmic decrement R_6 , which governs the rate of the shear softening of the material, and on the asymptotic parameter G_1 . Let us outline that there is no threshold to the shear nonlinearity.

The investigation of the tangent shear modulus response during the unloading/loading loops lead us to postulate that it obeyed in some manner a well known rule, i. e. the so-called Masing's rule, illustrated in Figure 2: for some plastic materials, there is an homothetic relationship of factor -2 between the response to the first loading OA and the response to the unloading AB . In particular, the modulus at the beginning of the unloading (point A) is the same as the initial modulus (point O).

FIGURE 2. Masing's rule

More precisely, we have found that the rate of decrease of the tangent shear modulus during unloadings was half the one during loadings. This is easily put in the exponential law expressed in equation (2) in doubling the logarithmic decrement R_6 . We have also found that the modulus at the beginning of unloadings was lesser than the initial modulus G_0 . So, we propose the following model for the loading/ unloading loops:

$$G = G'_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-|R - R_{\text{ext}}|}{2R_6}\right) \quad (3)$$

where R_{ext} is the extremum value reached during the preceding (un)loading phase, i.e.:

-during unloadings, $R_{\text{ext}} = R_{\text{max}}$ where R_{max} is the maximum shear strain reached during the preceding loading (A in Figure 3);

-during reloadings, $R_{\text{ext}} = R_{\text{min}}$, where R_{min} is the shear strain at the end of the preceding unloading (B in Figure 3).

The value of G'_0 in (3) was found to decrease as the cycle number increases. However, only few experimental points of the $G'_0(R_{\text{max}})$ curve were experimentally available, namely as many as the number of cycles. For sake of simplicity, the following exponential law is proposed:

$$G'_0 = (G_0 - G_{00}) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-R_{\text{max}}}{R_{00}}\right) + G_{00} \quad (4)$$

which is an exponential decrease from the initial value G_0 (same as in (2)) to the asymptotic value G_{00} .

Let us notice that equation (3) ensures closing of the cycles.

Our modeling is summarized in Figure (3):

FIGURE 3. Modeling of non monotonic tests

The identification of the different parameters was done graphically by superposition of the experimental and theoretical curves $\sigma_x(\epsilon_x)$. Indeed, the different parameters have very distinct effects on the computed responses: G_0 governs the initial slope, R_6 the curvature of the first loading curve, R_{00} and G_{00} the way the orientation of the cycles' axis varies. By dichotomic trial and error, it is easy to obtain a good fit between theoretical and experimental curves, as can be seen in Figures 4-5, corresponding to the parameters values listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Identified parameters values

Sample	E_1	E_2	ν_{12}	G_0	G_0^*	R_6	G_{00}	R_{00}
	GPa	GPa		GPa	GPa	%	GPa	%
[15]4S	43	10	0.3	4.5	4.33	1.0	3.25	1.0
[45]4S	43	10	0.3	4.3	4.3	1.0	3.25	1.0

The value denoted G_0^* is obtained from the apparent value G_0 after multiplying by the correction factor suggested by Pindera and Herakovich (8) to take into account the end constraint effects due to fixed grips. As can be seen in Table 1, the same set of parameters appears valid for both configurations.

FIGURE 4. Experimental (—) and modeled (--) responses for the $[15]_{4s}$ specimen

FIGURE 5. Experimental (—) and modeled (--) responses for the $[45]_{4s}$ specimen

CONCLUSION

A simple model has been proposed to describe the plastic behaviour of the unidirectional ply of polymer reinforced by long fibers. Only the shear nonlinearity is described, by means of the evolution of the tangent shear modulus with respect to the actual shear strain and to the previous extremum shear strain if any. A good correlation between theoretical and experimental responses has been obtained, and the identified parameters are the same for two different mechanical configurations ([15]_{4S} and [45]_{4S}). Nevertheless, evident viscoelastic effects have been observed (recovery) and should be taken into account in an improved modeling.

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